

Stirling's Approximation and Information Theory Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 8, 2025

To first order, Stirling's approximation is $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$. In general, there are more terms in a more accurate expression which is ultimately obtained through the method of steepest descent or other methods (1). In Part I, we used the idea that if N is very large and one has p_i probabilities, one would expect $\text{Product over } i \text{ } p_i^{\text{N} p_i} = 1/\text{number of arrangements}$. The number of arrangements is: $N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n_i!$ where $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } n_i = N$. Taking \ln of both sides and writing $p_i^{\text{N} p_i}$ as $\exp(N p_i \ln(p_i))$ leads to: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ immediately as shown in Part I. In Part I, we did not prove that $N p_i$ is the number of i results for $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$, this was considered an assumption.

Here we consider a different approach to finding the first order Stirling's approximation. We use $1 = (\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p_i)^N = \text{Sum (sets of } n_i) \text{ Product over } i \text{ } N! / n_i! \text{ Product over } i \text{ } p_i^{n_i}$ ((1)). A set of n_i means values for n_i such that $\text{Sum } n_i = N$. If one asks: What set of $\{n_i\}$ yields 1, i.e. completely exhausts the value of the sum ((1)), such that the other terms are essentially insignificant, i.e. 0? We find that the first order Stirling's approximation essentially yields this result. This then is equivalent to assuming that $N p_i$ is the expected number of occurrences for p_i and $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$.

Result of Part I

Stirling's approximation of $\ln(n!)$ may be obtained through the steepest descent method or other methods shown in (1) and involves various terms depending on the accuracy one seeks. To first order:

$$\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n) \quad ((1))$$

In Part I, we suggested a simple approach to obtaining ((1)). We calculated the probability of a set of N runs of events governed by p_i . With $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$, it was assumed, but not proven, that one expects:

$$N p_i \text{ results of event } i \text{ if } N \rightarrow \text{infinite} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Then: probability} = 1/\text{arrangements} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p_i^{\text{N} p_i} \quad ((3))$$

Using: $\text{number of arrangements} = \text{Product over } i \text{ } N! / n_i!$ and taking \ln off ((3)) leads to ((1)) as shown in Part I. Thus, it is the assumption ((2)) which is important in creating the first order term of Stirling's approximation.

Here we consider a different approach.

Second Approach to Find the First Order Stirling's Approximation

$$1 = \left\{ \sum_i p_i \right\}^N = \sum_i \frac{N!}{n_i!} \prod_i p_i^{n_i} \quad (4)$$

Here $\{n_i\}$ is a set of n_i positive integer values such that $\sum_i n_i = N$.

We ask: What set of n_i values makes one addend in the sum ((4)) equal to 1, i.e. completely dominates the sum such that the other terms are negligible. This is clearly an approximation, but one may find this value by taking \ln of ((4)):

$$\ln(1) = 0 = \ln(N!) - \sum_i \ln(n_i!) + \sum_i n_i \ln(p_i) \quad (5)$$

One may add: $0 = N \ln N = \sum_i n_i \ln(N)$ to the RHS of ((5)) yielding:

$$0 = \ln(1) = \ln(N!) - N \ln(N) + \sum_i n_i \ln(n_i) - \sum_i \ln(n_i!) \quad (6)$$

The result: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ ((7)) is a solution of ((6)) and hence one obtains a first order Stirling's approximation result.

From the first paragraph, one sees that this is equivalent to the expectation that for $N \rightarrow \infty$, $N p_i$ represents the number of times an event i appears in N trials.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Stirling's approximation may be obtained from a steepest descent method. The first order approximation is $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$. In Part I, we obtained this result in a simple manner by arguing that for $N \rightarrow \infty$ trials, $N p_i$ represents the number of times i appears. Then:
 $\frac{1}{\text{arrangements}} = \prod_i p_i^{N p_i}$ and $\text{arrangements} = \frac{N!}{n_i!}$.
 Taking \ln of both sides and equating yields: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$.

Here we use a different approach which does not make use of the a priori assumption that there are $N p_i$ results of i in $N \rightarrow \infty$ trials. We use: $\left(\sum_i p_i \right)^N = 1 = \sum_i \frac{N!}{n_i!} \prod_i p_i^{n_i}$, where $\{n_i\}$ is a set of n_i values such that $\sum_i n_i = N$. If one takes \ln of this expression and adds $\sum_i n_i \ln(N) - N \ln(N) = 0$ to the RHS, one obtains the first order Stirling's result: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stirling%27s_approximation